

Field Attachment and Teaching Practice Experiences of Technology Education Students in selected Universities in Kenya

Silyvier Tsindoli¹ and Lorna Wafula¹

¹Moi University, School of Education, Department of curriculum instruction and educational media

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Abstract

Field attachment and teaching practice play a vital role in shaping the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of technology education students. Through them, students explore the practical aspects of their teaching career and research. The study was guided by two objectives; First, to find out the imperative skills required for field attachment and teaching practice for technology students in Kenya and secondly, to find out the perception of technology students on field attachment and teaching practice in Kenya. The study adopted a qualitative research methodology and a descriptive research design. This study was anchored on David Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory. The target population consisted of third year Technology Education students from two public Universities in Kenya. Stratified and simple random sampling methods were used. Students who were in session for field attachment and teaching practice and those who had completed a year before were used. A total of 52 Technology Education students participated in the study from two public universities. Data was collected using using students' questionnaires that comprised of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. Data was analysed through descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. The study findings revealed that field attachment and teaching practice experiences of technology education students in Kenya are essential for their preparation as future technology educators and researchers. It was also evident that mentorship and support from experienced teachers and field supervisors played a significant role in the field attachment and teaching practice experiences. In conclusion, institutions should encourage their staff to mentor and support their attachees. In addition, the universities should align their curriculum with the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) requirements. The study recommended that educational institutions, Universities and policymakers prioritize the provision of adequate resources and support for technology education students during their field attachment and teaching practice.

Keywords: Field attachment, Teaching Practice, Technology Education

1.0 Introduction

Field attachment and teaching practice are integral components that play a crucial role in preparing Technology education students for the demands of the modern world by equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate a technology-driven society (Palm & Colucci-Gray, 2017). They provide students with practical training experiences to bridge the gap between theory and practice (Roberts & Johnson, 2020).

In this paper, field attachment is a field-based practical training experience that prepares teacher trainees for the tasks they are expected to perform on completion of their training. The purpose of field attachment and teaching practice at Moi University and University of Eldoret is to produce practically oriented graduates that meet the required job-related competences of their future employers. Additionally, it serves as a linkage between these University and various partners who consume services and/or products.

The objectives of the field attachment and teaching practice for Technology Education students in Moi university and University of Eldoret include the following: to enable students get hands-on/real life experiences they are expected to work in when they graduate, to provide an opportunity for students to apply the principles and techniques theoretically learnt into real-life problem solving situations, to provide an opportunity for teacher trainees to interact with the stakeholders and thus appreciate field situations that will also generate information for curricula review and improvement, to develop student understanding of work ethics, employment demands, responsibilities and opportunities and to enhance and strengthen linkages between Moi University, University of Eldoret and various stakeholders.

To make the field attachment and teaching practice a success, teacher trainees have specified roles and responsibilities which include the following: to take field attachment and teaching practice as part and parcel of their training at Moi University and University of Eldoret and have positive attitude towards learning by practice, respect all field supervisors and any other persons they interact with throughout their field attachment period regardless of their background training and social differentiation, work willingly wherever they are posted/attached, develop day-to-day work plans, adhere to the field attachment and teaching practice code of conduct and code of conduct of the host organizations, provide reports and other forms of feedback to the Universities.

Field attachment and teaching practice allow for the application of theoretical knowledge in real-world educational settings (Harris et al., 2020). During field attachment, students have the opportunity to observe and participate in classroom activities, gaining hands-on experience in lesson planning, instructional delivery, and student assessment (Johnson, 2017). This practical training enhances their understanding of pedagogical strategies and helps develop their skills as future technology educators (Smith & Brown, 2019).

Mentorship and support from experienced teachers are crucial components of field attachment and teaching practice experiences (Clark & Peterson, 2019). Mentors provide guidance, feedback, and encouragement to technology education students, fostering their professional growth and enhancing the quality of their practical training (Turner & Collins, 2021). Effective mentor-mentee relationships promote reflective practices, enabling students to critically analyze their teaching approaches and make necessary adjustments for better professional practices (Jones & Wilson, 2018). It was out of this background that the study sought to investigate Field Attachment and Teaching Practice Experiences of Technology Education Students in Kenya. This study is significant as it informs on the importance of field attachment and teaching practice and the best practices to be adopted by the universities to make these two components of the teacher training course meaningful.

Field attachment and teaching practice are key experiences in the teacher education programme. They are compulsory courses for all aspiring Technology Education (TED) student teachers registered in a teacher preparation programme. They are a way of establishing partnership between universities and schools/institutions for the preparation of student teachers. According to Otara (2014), field experience served as a functional tool to student teachers to get prepared for real world work experience and improve themselves as effective teachers.

Field attachment/teaching practice are meant to provide student teachers with experience to aid learning and appropriate positioning in the job market. They are some of the approaches used to promote university-community engagement through which experiential learning is promoted. Kolb (1984) states that experiential learning through action and reflection, helps student teachers to make sense of their environment, a process referred to by Moon (2004) as effective learning. With the increasingly changing and multicultural working environment, field attachments/teaching

practice enable TED student teachers to acquire interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary competencies in order to positively influence real development processes (Adomânt et al. 2014; Lambrechts et al. 2013). Students also gain cognitive experience by reflecting on field activities and processes during field attachment/teaching practice.

Dewey (1938) stated that reflective practice is the key for meaningful learning. He advocated for experiential teacher education which emphasizes on student-centered learning. He emphasizes that students should not try only what they have learned and believed; instead, they should learn from others such as mentors, supervisors, peers and also from literature. In this way, student teachers may be challenged to reconstruct what they know with what they have learned as a good practicum is the place where student teachers are challenged.

In teacher training programs, two types of knowledge are handled: received knowledge and experiential knowledge. Received knowledge includes theoretical knowledge given by experts; and experiential knowledge is acquired by a trainee's direct interaction with real teaching practice (Wallace, 1991). To apply what they have learnt as received knowledge in real life teaching context, gaining experience is the key factor for student teachers. As a result, the theoretical and practical knowledge student-teachers are given in teacher training programs has the utmost importance because preparing pre-service teachers shapes future in-service teachers (Tercanlıoğlu, 2008; Yıldız et al., 2016).

Zeichner (2002) notes that one of the purposes of Field attachment/Teaching practice should be to develop professional identities in student teachers. However, Student teachers cannot be prepared for every possible situation in their career. This suggests that student teachers should be provided with an efficient program that supplies them with rich experiences as much as possible. Khamasi et al., (2016), suggests that student teachers should be equipped with tools necessary for development and emphasize the importance of reflection. Abiero (2019) emphasized the importance of collaboration with peers, supervisors, and mentors. Through hands-on experiences in well-equipped workshops and laboratories, students gain proficiency in using tools, equipment, and technologies relevant to their field (Abiero, 2019; Khamasi et al., 2016).

The role of the faculty supervisors is also a crucial component of an effective teacher training program. Wilson (2006) explains that supervisors should not just give feedback to students for the

sake of it but also mentor the student teacher mentors about teacher education and teaching practice. Ulvick and Smith (2011) state that Reflective practices are key components of field attachment and teaching practice. They further explain that engaging in reflective activities allows students to critically analyze their teaching experiences, identify areas for improvement, and enhance their instructional strategies.

Stofflet and Stodart (1994), address the issue of collaborative learning and networking during field attachment/teaching practice. They state that collaboration with peers, educators, and faculty supervisors during field attachment and teaching practice enhance students' learning experiences. They provide opportunities for knowledge sharing, building professional networks, and exposure to the latest trends and field practices.

According to Hamaidi, Al-Shara, Arouri, & Awwad (2014), what the student teachers think about field work/teaching practice is also a critical issue as they are the ones who are trained to be teachers. Ulvik and Smith, (2011) show that student teachers have different opinions on their practical experiences. They find some aspects efficient and others inefficient. They also make quite beneficial suggestions to improve the programs. They identify some of areas on which students' opinions are based. They include: quality of mentorship and feedback, autonomy and responsibility given to student teachers, diverse experiences, the school environment, experiencing the comprehensive role of a teacher and having a structured programme.

The field attachment and teaching practice of TED students is faced with several challenges that hinder the effective acquisition of practical skills and teaching experience. Hamaidi et al, (2014) observe that there is a gap between university courses and real-life classrooms, vague definition of practice, and lack of support in the field. Similarly, Gan, (2013) indicate that students in the field have difficulty in applying theory into practice. They also face the challenge of unsupportive attitude of mentors, classroom management. There is also an existing gap between what they were taught at the university and the practice in the field. Even though student teachers are exposed to up-to-date teaching methods, they observe that there is no change in schools in terms of new instructional ways. Therefore, there is a need to change educational practices to break the circle of traditionally trained teachers who teach in a traditional manner (Stofflett & Stoddart, 1994).

Fahmy and Bilton (1992) identify several challenges that students in the field face. First, student teachers have problems with English proficiency, especially with grammar and oral skills. Second challenge is limited access to appropriate learning environments: Technology education requires access to well-equipped workshops, laboratories, and classrooms to provide hands-on experience to students. However, many institutions struggle to provide adequate resources, resulting in a lack of practical exposure for students during their field attachment and teaching practice. Thirdly students face the challenge of insufficient integration of real-world applications in the field attachment. Technology education aims to prepare students for real-world applications of their skills. However, the current field attachment and teaching practice programs often lack sufficient integration of real-world projects and problem-solving activities. This leads to a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical skills, limiting students' ability to apply what they have learned.

In addition, Inadequate supervision and mentoring: Field attachment and teaching practice programs require effective supervision and mentoring to guide students in their learning process. However, limited resources and a high student-to-teacher ratio often result in insufficient individual attention and guidance for students. This can hinder their professional growth and development. Limited collaboration with field professionals and little support and mentorship from institution staff during attachments: Technology is a rapidly evolving field, and it is crucial for students to engage with field professionals during their field attachment and teaching practice. However, there is often a lack of collaboration between educational institutions and the Universities, which limits students' exposure to the latest technologies, trends, and field practices.

Finally, inconsistent assessment and evaluation: Assessment and evaluation methods for field attachment and teaching practice vary across institutions, leading to inconsistencies in grading and feedback. This lack of standardization can affect students' motivation and hinder their ability to receive constructive feedback for improvement.

The challenges that TED student teachers face will make them reconstruct their previous knowledge and beliefs with the help of the information they get from the practice, mentors, peers, supervisors, and theory. Besides, the challenges the students face are of utmost importance for supervisors as they are the ones preparing the teacher training programs. Considering the

challenges, the students and the supervisors can rethink about possible ways to make the program more effective and fruitful (Ngwaru, 2013)

According to the literature, learning at the University is quite theoretical. Therefore, it is important to provide students with opportunities to apply their knowledge to the real world through field attachment and teaching practice. By getting attached to TVET institutions and schools, Technology Education students gain professional experience by observing and learning from experienced educators and field professionals. These experiences enhance their understanding of instructional methods, pedagogical competencies, collaboration and networking, classroom management, curriculum development, and field practices, thus preparing them for future roles. Therefore, the study was guided by two research objectives which were to find out the imperative skills acquired during field attachment and teaching practice by technology Education students and to find out the perception of technology students on field attachment and teaching practice.

2.0 Methodology

The target population consisted of third year Technology Education students from two public Universities in Kenya. Moi university and University of Eldoret were selected purposively for convenience of the researcher to access the participants. Stratified and simple random sampling methods were used to get the samples. Students who were in session for field attachment and teaching practice and those who had completed a year before were used. A total of 52 Technology Education students participated in the study from the two public universities. Data was collected using questionnaires. Data was analysed through descriptive statistics and thematic analysis.

3.0 Findings and Discussion

The study was guided by two research objectives; to find out the imperative skills acquired during field attachment and teaching practice by technology Education students and to find out the perception of technology students on field attachment and teaching practice.

The respondents comprised of 52 third year Technology Education students who had completed industrial attachment and teaching practicum from two public universities. 56 (49.1%) were female and 58 (50.9%) were male as presented in Figure 1.

Figure1: Demographic information

Skills acquired during field attachment and teaching practice

Data was collected concerning competency of skills acquired/polished during field attachment and teaching practice of Technology Education students. Table 1 indicate that, majority of field work and teaching practice helped TED students to polish their critical thinking, creativity, innovation, problem solving, communication skills, collaboration, digital skills, networking, team work and leadership skills.

Table 1: Skills acquired and polished during field attachment and teaching practice

Skills	Very competent	Fairly Competent	Not Competent	Total
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Critical thinking	24 (46.1%)	16 (30.8%)	12 (23.1%)	52 (100%)
Creativity	22 (42.3%)	16 (30.8%)	14 (26.9%)	52 (100%)
Innovation	12 (23.1%)	29 (55.8%)	11 (21.2%)	52 (100%)
Problem solving	16 (30.8%)	24 (46.2%)	12 (23.1%)	52 (100%)
Communication skills	29 (55.8%)	20 (38.5%)	9 (17.3%)	52 (100%)
Collaboration	23 (20.2%)	15 (28.8%)	14 (12.3%)	52 (100%)
Digital skills	22 (42.3%)	16 (30.8%)	14 (26.9%)	52 (100%)
Networking	20 (38.5%)	13 (25%)	19 (36.5%)	52 (100%)
Team work	24 (46.1%)	16 (30.8%)	12 (23.1%)	52 (100%)
Leadership	15 (28.8%)	23 (20.2%)	14 (12.3%)	52 (100%)

On the other hand, from the qualitative data, respondents indicated that for them to be equipped with imperative skills, the universities should align its curriculum to the technical college curriculum, emphasize on workshop practical and provide more modern resources for the practical. The technical vocational training institutions (TVET) on the other side should improve on the

structures on students' discipline, integrate information technology communication skills, split the large classes, and involve trainees on attachment in seminars, workshops and mentorship programmes. Respondents emphasized on integration of technology within technology education. Studies emphasize the role of technology as a tool for enhancing teaching and learning processes, promoting engagement, and fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Chen & Wang, 2018). However, challenges such as limited technology infrastructure and teachers' proficiency in technology integration need to be addressed for effective implementation (García-Sánchez & Ferreira, 2021).

Field attachment and teaching practice are necessary for knowledge and skills acquisition. Practical training experiences allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world educational settings. Through field attachment, students gain hands-on experience in lesson planning, instructional delivery, and student assessment which enhance their understanding of pedagogical strategies.

Perception of technology students on field attachment and teaching practice.

Qualitative data indicated that, field attachment and teaching practice are both necessary for acquiring knowledge and skills. However, majority of the respondents said that field attachment should precede teaching practice. They said that field attachment helped them to relate practical skills with theory learned and would complement teaching practice. Studies have consistently highlighted the importance of field attachment and teaching practice in technology education programs. Practical training experiences allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world educational settings (Harris et al., 2020). Through field attachment, students gain hands-on experience in lesson planning, instructional delivery, and student assessment, which enhance their understanding of pedagogical strategies (Johnson, 2017). The teaching practice component provides opportunities for students to further develop their skills as future technology educators (Smith & Brown, 2019).

Question: Field attachment and teaching practice are core practices for one to complete his/her training for technology students in Kenya, from your experience which one should begin and why?

- *Field attachment, Because it exposes students and gives better understanding on taught experience*
- *Field attachment then teaching practice so to gain visual experience to what to teach on teaching practice*

- *Field attachment should begin since one will gain experience and have a clear picture of what to teach according to your area of specialization*
- *Field attachment should start simply because one will get the basic knowledge/skills from the field which will enable his or her teaching career to be effective in class while delivering the content when teaching student. you can teach skill course without basics.*

Majority of the respondent indicated that they obtained theoretical knowledge in their respective field of specialization. On the other hand field work and teaching practice helped them to polish their communication skills, critical thinking, problem solving, digital skills, creativity, confidence, team work, collaboration, time management, networking, and leadership and innovation skills. Findings indicated that supervision and mentorship done during field attachment and teaching practice was adequate and meaningful however they received little support and mentorship from institution staff during attachment. Mentorship and support from experienced teachers play a significant role in the field attachment and teaching practice experiences of technology education students. Effective mentor-mentee relationships contribute to students' professional growth by providing guidance, feedback, and opportunities for reflection (Clark & Peterson, 2019). Mentors help students bridge the gap between theory and practice, offering valuable insights and nurturing their development as competent educators (Turner & Collins, 2021).

Constraints faced by technology students during field attachment and teaching practice

Table 2 shows the constraints faced by technology students during field attachment and teaching practice. Majority indicated that limited knowledge from undergraduate training, limited mentorship from the institutions they are posted and limited mentorship from the Teaching practice coordinators and assessors from the university are the most serious challenges they face. While majority said that collaborations with other students on field attachment and teaching practice is a mild challenge. However, Majority of the responded said that time allocated for field attachment and teaching practice is sufficient.

Table 2: Constrains faced by technology students during field attachment and teaching practice

Issues	A serious challenge	A mild challenge	Not at all
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Limited knowledge from my undergraduate training	23 (44.2)	17 (32.7)	12 (23.1)
Limited mentorship from the institutions they are posted	29 (55.8)	20 (38.5)	9 (17.3)
Limited mentorship from the Teaching practice coordinators and assessors from the university	24 (46.1)	16 (30.8)	12 (23.1)
Limited time for field attachment and teaching practice	9(17.3)	10 (19.2)	33 (63.5)
Limited collaborations with other students on TP	7(13.5)	39 (75.0)	6 (11.5)

Findings obtained from qualitative data indicated that, majority of the respondents face the following constrains; poor class turn out from students, indiscipline learners, lack of support from institutional staff, inadequate resources to march the large classes, inadequate skills from the university training and gaps between what they have learnt and application. Limited resources and equipment hinder effective instruction and limit hands-on learning experiences (Nyagah & Ondigi, 2018). Additionally, large class sizes and time constraints pose difficulties in providing individualized attention to students and delivering quality instruction (Kiboss & Mutembei, 2020).

The study also revealed that Universities should align their curriculum to the TVET curriculum and emphasize on practical knowledge. On the other hand, TVET institutions and schools should improve on facilities, students' discipline, integrate information communication technology (ICT) skills, split the large classes, and involve trainees on attachment in seminars, workshops and mentorship programmes.

Mentorship and support from experienced teachers, field officers and lecturers play a significant role in the field attachment and teaching practice experiences of technology education students. Effective mentor-mentee relationships contribute to students' professional growth by providing

guidance, feedback and opportunities for reflection. Mentors help students bridge the gap between theory and practice, offering valuable insights and nurturing their development.

Question: What constraints have you experienced during the field attachment period and how do you think those constraints could be overcome?

- *Lack of enough learning Materials, government to intervene to help*
- *poor turnout by students*
- *"Harassments from supervisors and other workers towards attaches*
- *Loading of subject and time limited.*
- *Lecture hall wasn't favorable. Time management, By planning yourself early enough*
- *"time management most of the students are delaying attending the lecture, this can be overcome by making sure that if you did not attend the class you will not sit for exam*
- *lack of teaching materials where by to find the textbooks to be used is difficult,, They must ensure that there is enough teaching materials in the institution "*
- *Little skills from the University, university should provide practicals before field attachment*
- *"Time management since concept gained was a bit new and adjusting to it as well. To overcome is to offer more practice on it*
- *Inadequate skills- give more practicals classes to ensure that one is well equipped with hands on skills during the field attachment*
- *New technology I overcame by help of doing more research*

4.0 Conclusions

Field attachment/teaching practice is essential for TED students in Kenya for professional development and preparation as future technology educators and researchers.

Field attachment should precede teaching practice to lay ground for knowledge and skills acquisition that are applicable to pedagogical practices.

Field attachment/teaching practice will help students acquire the following skills; communication skills, critical thinking, problem solving, digital skills, creativity, confidence, team work, collaboration, time management, networking, leadership and innovative skills.

For technology students to be equipped with imperative skills, the universities should align its curriculum to the TVET curriculum, emphasize on hands on practices and provide modern resources for the practicals. The TVET should improve on the structures on students' discipline, integrate ICT in their practice, split the large classes, and involve trainees on attachment in seminars, workshops and mentorship programmes.

5.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the questionnaire on the field attachment and teaching practice experiences of TED students, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the practical training and professional development of these students:

Student teachers should be exposed to programmes that focus on enhancing their proficiency in utilizing technological tools, polishing their communication skills, critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, confidence, team work, collaboration, time management, networking, leadership and innovation skills.

Educational institutions should foster supportive mentor-mentee relationships between experienced teachers and TED student teachers. Mentors should provide guidance, feedback, and opportunities for reflection to facilitate students' professional growth

Universities should develop and implement policies that prioritize hands on experiences such as field attachment and teaching practice experiences.

There is also a need to change educational practices to break the circle of traditionally trained teachers who use traditional pedagogies.

6.0 Declaration of Interest

There are no competing interests in this paper

7.0 References

- Abiero, M.O. (2009). Curriculum Development. Longhorn publishers, Nairobi
- Adomânt, M., Fischer, D., Godemann, J., Herzig, C., Otte, I., Rceckmann, M. and Timm, J. (2014). Emerging areas in research on higher education, sustainable development, management education, sustainable consumption and perspectives from Central and Eastern Europe. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 62:1-7.

- Colucci-Gray, L., Burnard, P., Aberdeen, C.C., Gray, D., Trowsdale, J. (2017). A report from one of the BERA Research Commissions.
- Dewey, J. (1938). Experience and Education. The Journal of the Society.Kappa Delta Pi, 1938, ISBN 0-684-83828-1
- Hamaidi, D., Al-Shara, I., Arouri, Y and Awwad F. (2014) A Student- Teachers' Perspectives of Practicum Practices and Challenges. *European Scientific Journal edition vol.10, No.13* ISSN: 1857-7881: <https://ro.ecu.edu.au/ajte>
- Improving graduate competencies through field attachments: Experiences from the School of Agricultural Sciences, Makerere University Opolot, H.N.1 , Isubikalu, P. 1 , Obaa, B.B.1 & Ebanyat, P. 1
- Kiplagat, K. H, Karei, R. (2016). Students; Experiences of Industrial Attachment: A Case of a Public University in Kenya. *E-Journal of African Studies in Educational Management and Leadership*, Vol.7. 1, pp82-97
- Kolb, D.D. 1984. Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development. Prentice Hall, Inc. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.
- Lambrechts, W., Mula, I., Ceulemans, K., Molderez, I. and Gaeremynck, V. 2013. The integration of competencies for sustainable development in higher education: an analysis of bachelor programmes in management. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 48:65-73.
- McLennan, H., Roberts, J.m& Johnson, G. (2023). Stakeholder Experience Evaluating Whole-School Practice Designed to Improve Educational Outcomes for Autistic Students. Published online by Cambridge University Press: 02 May 2023
- Moon, J. 2004. A Handbook of Reflective and Experiential Learning: Theory and Practice. RoutledgeFalmer, London. 258 pp.
- Ngwaru, C. (2013). Pre-Service Student Teacher Practices in the Teaching of English as a Second Language: Experiences, Opportunities and Challenges. Published 20 September 2013. *Greener Journal of Educational Research*
- Otara, A. (2014). Students' Perceptions on Education Internship Program in Rwanda: Effectiveness and Challenges. *European Journal of Educational Sciences*, v1 n2 p181-193 Jun 2014

- Smith, S.V and Brown, S. (2019) PhD Published Work: is it time to clarify and tighten-up the ground rules? Association of National Teaching Fellows. Link to Leeds Beckett Repository record: <https://eprints.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/id/eprint/5640/>
- Stofflett, R.T., & Stoddart, T. (1994). The ability to understand and use conceptual change pedagogy as a function of prior content learning experience. First published: January 1994 <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.3660310105>
- Turner, H., Christine, M., Rubie D., & Melinda, W. (2015). Teacher Expectations, Ethnicity and the Achievement Gap March 2015 New Zealand Journal of Educational Studies 50(1) DOI:10.1007/s40841-015-0004-1
- Ulvik, M. & Smith, K. (2011). Published online: 01 Sep 2011 <https://doi.org/10.3402/edui.v2i3.21997> Pages 517-536
- Wallace, J (1991). https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-Reflective-Model-of-Professional-Development-p-49_fig1_301316636
- Wilson M. S. (2006). How Can We Improve Teacher Quality? <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172171109300214>
- Zeichner, K. (2002). Beyond Traditional Structures of Student Teaching. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 29, 59-64.